

On Colloidal Electrolytes

An Attempt to Account for the Osmotic Pressure of Sols of Gum Arabic when the Concentration of the Gum and that of the Diffusible Electrolytes Added Vary

B. N. GHOSH

Department of Pure Chemistry, Calcutta University, Calcutta 9

Manuscript received 23 June 1972; revised 18 September 1972; accepted 26 December 1972

On the basis of a new mode of approach, equations have been deduced to account for the osmotic pressure of sols of gum arabic under conditions in which the concentration of the gum and that of the diffusible electrolytes added to the system are varied. The equations have been found to agree well with the experimental data. The deduction of the equations involves an interpretation of the Donnan theory of membrane equilibrium somewhat different from that offered so far. It has been shown that when the sol is dilute, so that the average distance between the surfaces of two neighbouring particles is quite large compared to the thickness of the electrical double layer surrounding them and the potential in the intermicellar liquid due to the double layers is zero, then the activity of each kind of diffusible ions in the intermicellar liquid is equal to the activity of the same kind of ions in the outer chamber containing the aqueous solution of the diffusible ions only.

IT has been shown from theoretical considerations, in a previous paper¹, that if $(H)_c$ represents the activity of the counter ions in a sol of a colloidal electrolyte H_2G of concentration C and $(H)_t$ the activity of the counter ions in the intermicellar liquid of the sol then the following equation holds good when the sol is diluted

$$(H)_c - (H)_t = \theta[(H)_s - (H)_t] \quad (1)$$

In equation (1) $(H)_s$ is a proportionality constant which may be interpreted to represent the activity of the counter ions within the diffuse double layer, associated with a unit area, at the plane of contact with the reversible electrode and $\theta = \frac{C}{K_0 + C}$ where C represent the concentration of the colloid expressed in an arbitrary unit and K_0 a constant.

The main assumptions on the basis of which the equation (1) has been derived are (1) that a colloidal particle is surrounded by an electrical double layer consisting of the fixed Stern²-Mukherjee³ layer and the diffuse Gouy⁴-Chapman⁵ layer and (2) that the counter ions in the diffuse double layer of a colloidal particle can record their activity only when the particle carries them sufficiently close to the electrode so that they come in contact with it.

If to the sol of the colloidal electrolyte H_2G a small quantity of a uni-univalent strong electrolyte H^+A^- is added then at equilibrium, the diffuse double layers of the colloidal particles shall contain the counter ions H^+ in plenty and a few co-ions A^- and the intermicellar liquid shall also contain the H^+ and

A^- ions. The activity of the counter ions $(H)_c$ and of the Co-ions $(A)_c$ in the sol can be written as

$$(H)_c - (H)_t = \theta[(H)_s - (H)_t] \quad (1a)$$

$$(A)_c - (A)_t = \theta[(A)_s - (A)_t] \quad (1b)$$

In the equations (1a) and (1b), $(H)_s$ and $(A)_s$ are proportionality constants having the same significance as that of $(H)_s$ in equation (1), $(H)_t$ and $(A)_t$ represent the activity of H^+ and A^- ions in the intermicellar liquid and θ is the same as in equation (1).

The equations (1a) and (1b) can be derived by following the same line of argument as has been used for the derivation of equation (1).

In this paper the extent to which the aforesaid equations can be adapted to the conditions of Donnan equilibria will be considered.

According to Donnan's theory⁶ of membrane equilibria, for a system consisting of a strong electrolyte H^+A^- and a colloidal electrolyte H_2G where G represents the colloidal anion of valency Z and H^+ the counter ions, the following equations should hold good,

$$P = RT[(H)_c + (A)_c - (H)_0 - (A)_0] + RTG \quad (2)$$

and

$$\frac{(H)_c}{(H)_0} = \frac{(A)_0}{(A)_c} = R \quad (2a)$$

where $(H)_c$, $(A)_c$ and G represent the activity of the

counter ions, co-ions and the colloidal anions respectively inside the colloid chamber and $(H)_0$ and $(A)_0$ the activity of the counter ions and the co-ions in the outside chamber containing the aqueous solution of the diffusible ions only, the two chambers being separated by a membrane through which the diffusible ions only can pass. It may be mentioned that it has not been possible to evaluate $(H)_c$ and $(A)_c$ from their respective concentration multiplied by the corresponding activity coefficient although attempts have been made in the past to find the correct activity coefficients on the basis of plausible assumptions. The various assumptions about the activity coefficients have been criticised by Klaarenbeek⁷.

Usually the term involving G in equation (2) is very small compared to the other terms and it may be neglected. The equation (2) may then be written as

$$P = RT[(H)_c + (A)_c - (H)_0 - (A)_0] \quad (2b)$$

$$= RT D \quad (2c)$$

where D has been put equal to $[(H)_c + (A)_c - (H)_0 - (A)_0]$ and represents the excess activity of the diffusible ions in the colloid chamber.

It may be pointed out that if the equations (1a) and (1b) are added together then the following equation is obtained.

$$\begin{aligned} [(H)_c + (A)_c - (H)_i - (A)_i] \\ = \theta[(H)_s + (A)_s - (H)_i - (A)_i] \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

A comparison of the left hand side term of equation (3) with the right hand side term within the square bracket of equation (2b) shows that $(H)_c$ and $(A)_c$ are identical, as in both the equations they represent the activity of the counter ions and co-ions respectively in the colloid chamber, but $(H)_i$ and $(A)_i$ represent the activity of the counter ions and the co-ions respectively in the intermicellar liquid in the colloid chamber while $(H)_0$ and $(A)_0$ represent respectively the activity of these ions in the outside chamber containing the aqueous solution only.

It can, however, be proved that in a dilute colloidal solution in which the average distance between the surfaces of two neighbouring colloidal particles is quite large⁺ compared to the thickness of the electrical double layer then, under the conditions of Donnan membrane, equilibrium, $(H)_i = (H)_0$ and $(A)_i = (A)_0$.

Let us consider two chambers separated by a membrane through which water and the ions of the

diffusible electrolyte can pass but the colloidal ions cannot. Let the chamber containing the colloidal electrolyte H_2G and the ions H^+ and A^- of the diffusible electrolyte be denoted as inside chamber and the other chamber containing the aqueous solution of the ions H^+ and A^- of the diffusible electrolyte be denoted as outside chamber. In the inside chamber, at equilibrium, let $(H)_c$ and $(A)_c$ denote the total activity of the counter ions and co-ions respectively and $(H)_i$ and $(A)_i$ the activity respectively of these ions in the intermicellar liquid. Similarly in the outside chamber let the activity of the aforesaid ions be denoted by $(H)_0$ and $(A)_0$ respectively. Then for the ions in the inside chamber the equations (1a), (1b) and hence (3) hold good. Suppose at a concentration C of the colloid, the fraction θ of the surface of the membrane per unit area on the colloid side is covered by the double layers of the colloidal particles and the remaining fraction $(1-\theta)$ is in contact with the ions H^+ and A^- of the intermicellar liquid of activity $(H)_i$ and $(A)_i$ respectively. Since the electric field of the double layers does not extend beyond their boundaries and since they are far apart in a dilute sol, therefore, in the intermicellar liquid the potential due to the double layers is zero and hence to satisfy the condition of electroneutrality $(H)_i = (A)_i$. In the region $(1-\theta)$ of the membrane, therefore, $(H)_i = (A)_i$ and since Donnan equilibria requires that $(H)_i \times (A)_i = (H)_0 \times (A)_0$, so we find that $(H)_i = (H)_0 = (A)_i = (A)_0$.

Let us next consider the region θ of the membrane with which the double layers of some of the colloidal ions are in contact on the colloid side and the diffusible ions of activity $(H)_0$ and $(A)_0$ on the outside. Let E_s be the potential of the plane of the double layer which is in contact with the membrane. Then according to Boltzmann law, the activity $(H)_s$ of the counter ions in that plane is equal to $(H)_i \exp^{eE_s/kT}$ and that of the co-ions $(A)_s$ is equal to $(A)_i \exp^{-eE_s/kT}$ where e is the elementary charge and the other terms have their usual significance. Therefore, in the region θ of the membrane $(H)_s \times (A)_s = (H)_i \times (A)_i \exp^{eE_s/kT} \times \exp^{-eE_s/kT} = (H)_i \times (A)_i$ although $(H)_s$ is much greater than $(A)_s$ and is responsible for the unequal distribution of the diffusible ions on the two sides of the membrane.

Now substituting $(H)_i$ and $(A)_i$ by $(H)_0$ and $(A)_0$ respectively in equation (3) and multiplying both sides of it by RT we get

$$P = RT[(H)_c + (A)_c - (H)_0 - (A)_0] \quad (4)$$

$$= RT\theta[(H)_s + (A)_s - (H)_0 - (A)_0] \quad (4a)$$

It will be noticed that equation (4) is identical with equation (2b). Putting D_s equal to $[(H)_s + (A)_s - (H)_0 - (A)_0]$ in equation (4a) we can write these equations as,

$$P = RTD \quad (5)$$

$$P = RT\theta D_s \quad (5a)$$

It may be pointed out that D_s is greater than D but $\theta D_s = D$.

⁺ The aforesaid description of a dilute colloidal soln. is consistent with the view expressed by Overbeek⁸. He writes, "This fact that even at very high dilution of the colloidal particles the Donnan theory for ideal behaviour is not followed, is one of the strongest indications of the necessity of considering a dilute solution of a colloid as a number of islands of high concentration of ions dispersed in a solution of a much lower concentration, rather than as a completely homogeneous system".

Osmotic pressure of arabic acid sol under conditions of Donnan equilibria :

Measurement of osmotic pressure of purified gum arabic acid sol has been made by Briggs⁹ under conditions in which the concentration of the gum, sodium chloride, hydrochloric acid and caustic soda has been varied selectively. The activity of the H ions in the inside and outside chambers has been measured by the potentiometric method and their ratio, *R*, has been found. The concentration of each kind of ions Na⁺ and Cl⁻ in the inside and outside chambers has been calculated from a knowledge of their total amount and the volume *V_i* and *V_o* of the solutions in the two chambers using the ratio *R*. Briggs has further assumed that the concentrations of the ions are equal to their activities. In this way Briggs has determined a quantity *D_w* which he has taken to be equal to the excess ion activity *D* and has calculated the osmotic pressure using the equation

$$P = RTD_w \quad (5b)$$

His calculated osmotic pressure has been found to be much greater than the observed value. Since Briggs has used concentration instead of activity his *D_w* is greater than *D* of equation (2c) for reasons stated already. It may, however, be proportional to *D_s* and so the following equation has been tried,

$$P = RT \theta KD_w \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) is also obtained by putting $\theta KD_w = D$ in equation (2c) or (5). It has been found that equation (6) agrees well with the experimental data when the solution in the inside chamber is distinctly acid i.e., pH usually below 3.3 but in some cases it may extend up to 3.7.

Determination of the Constants K and K₀ in θ :

It follows from equation (6) that

$$\frac{P}{RTD_w} = \theta K = K \frac{C}{K_0 + C} \quad (7)$$

In equation (7) *RT* at 25° is equal to 25280 cm of water. Knowing the values of *P* and *C* for two selected values of *D_w* and putting them in equation (7), two equations are obtained in which all the quantities are known except *K* and *K₀*. Hence *K* and *K₀* can easily be found. It may be mentioned that *K₀* (= 43.3) remains constant throughout, but *K* varies as the experimental conditions are altered.

Briggs has also measured the osmotic pressure of gum arabic sols in which the concentration of NaOH is greater than that of HCl. In one set of experiments (*L*) the amount of HCl has been kept constant but the amount of NaOH has been varied while in the other set of experiments (*M*) the concentrations of both HCl and NaOH have been varied. In these cases, the values of *D_w* determined by Briggs are found unsuitable for the calculation of the true value of osmotic pressure. It appears that when NaOH

is in excess over HCl, the H⁺ ion activity is small and error in its determination is relatively large and this causes a large error in the value of *R*. Hence *D_w* estimated by using such erroneous value of *R* becomes unsuitable.

An analysis of the terms involved in equation (4a) under these conditions has proved useful in deciding which of the variables in it may be used in place of *D_w*. The equation under the conditions of these experiments may be written as

$$P = RT\theta[(H)_s + (Na)_s + (Cl)_s - (H)_0 - (Na)_0 - (Cl)_0] \quad (8)$$

It may be mentioned that the exchangeable H⁺ ions per gram of arabic acid are fixed and when the total Cl content, at constant volume is also fixed but the NaOH is increased its amount in equivalents being greater than that of HCl, the arabic acid is neutralised more and more. The entire amount of NaOH added enters the diffuse double layer, the (OH) ions neutralise the H⁺ ions there and Na⁺ ions take the place of the H⁺ ions neutralised. To restore equilibrium fresh H⁺ ions are released from the Stern-Mukherjee layer. Thus the (Na)_s increases proportionately with NaOH as more and more of it is added. Of the other terms, although (H)_s decreases yet it always remains much greater than (H)₀. Furthermore, the terms (H)_s + (Cl)_s - (H)₀ - (Na)₀ - (Cl)₀ cancel each other to a considerable extent leaving an excess (Cl)₀ which, is quite small compared to (Na)_s. This residual (Cl)₀ however, increases at the expense of (Cl)_s. So *K₁*(Na)_s may be substituted for (Cl)₀ where *K₁* is a constant much smaller than unity. Equation (8) may then be written as

$$P = RT\theta[(Na)_s(1 - K_1)] \quad (9)$$

The only variable now within the square bracket in equation (9) is (Na)_s and at a constant volume of the solution it may be taken as proportional to (NaOH) per gram of gum used. Therefore, the following equation may be used

$$P = RT\theta K[(Na)] \quad (10)$$

where [(Na)] represents the concentration of NaOH per gram of gum used and *K* is a proportionality constant.

Under the conditions (*M*), from reasonings similar to that recorded above and taking note of the fact that the Cl⁻ content is also varied, at constant volume of the solution, the following equation has been used

$$P = RT\theta K[(Na) - (Cl)] \quad (11)$$

where [(Na) - (Cl)] represents the concentration of NaOH in excess over HCl per gram of the gum used.

The equations (10) and (11) have been found to agree well with the experimental data of Briggs.

Notes on the Contents of the Tables

In Table I are recorded the data taken from Table 1 of Briggs paper⁹. The composition of the

+ Since at this stage the entire amount of NaOH added enters the diffuse double layer so (Na)₀ does not increase.

outside solution has been kept constant and the volume of the solution is 3000 ml. After the system attained equilibrium, the values of D_w has been determined by Briggs by adopting the procedure discussed already. θ in the Tables 1 to 3a is equal to $C/(K_0+C)$ where C represents the concentration of gum arabic per 1000 grams of water and K_0 is a constant equal to 43.3.

The data in the Tables 2 and 2a have been taken from Table 2 of Briggs paper⁹. The volume of the solution taken in the outside chamber is 320 ml. In these experiments the applied external pressure and the amount of HCl have been kept constant while the amount of NaOH has been varied. The colloid, therefore, dilutes itself until at equilibrium

the osmotic pressure becomes equal to the applied external pressure. In column 4 of Table 2a are recorded the values of $[(Na^+)]$ per gram of the gum used.

The data recorded in the Tables 3 and 3a have been taken from Table 4 of Briggs paper⁹. The volume of the solution taken in the outside chamber is 320 ml. and the concentrations of both (Na^+) and (Cl^-) are varied. In column 6 of table 3 are recorded the values of $[(Na^+)-(Cl^-)]$ per gram of the gum used. In these experiments also the applied external pressure has been kept constant. For further details one may consult the original paper of Briggs⁹. For the calculation of osmotic pressure RT at 25° has been taken as equal to 25.28×10^3 cm of H_2O .

TABLE 1—EXTERNAL SOLUTION OF CONSTANT COMPOSITION

Vol. 3000 ml $(Na^+) = 0.85 \times 10^{-3}$ equiv/L
 $(Cl)^- = 1.504 \times 10^{-3}$ equiv/L

K_0 (in θ) = 43.3
 K in eqn. (7) = 1.25.

Expt. No.	Con. of gum C	pH of solution in colloid chamber	Excess con. $D_w \times 10^3$	θ	Osmotic pressure in cm. H_2O		
					Observed	Calculated from	
						Author's eqn. (6)	Briggs eqn. (5b)
1	19.94	2.72	1.433	0.315	14.5	14.3	36.3
2	26.67	2.64	2.148	0.381	27.3	25.9	54.2
3	31.90	2.58	2.796	0.424	37.8	37.5	70.7
3	37.93	2.54	3.257	0.467	48.7	48.1	82.4
5	54.82	2.44	4.662	0.559	85.7	82.4	117.8
6	60.13	2.40	5.332	0.581	97.4	97.9	134.8
7	64.13	2.40	5.832	0.599	110.5	110.4	147.5
8	67.74	2.36	6.208	0.610	119.5	119.7	157.1

TABLE 2—COMPOSITION OF EXTERNAL SOLUTION (Na) VARYING BUT (Cl) CONSTANT

K_0 (in θ) = 43.3
 K in eqn. (7) = 1.225

Expt. No.	Con. of gum C	pH of solution in colloid chamber	Excess con. $D_w \times 10^3$	θ	Osmotic pressure in cm. H_2O		
					Observed	Calculated from	
						Author's eqn. (6)	Briggs eqn. (5b)
1	83.9	2.27	6.24	0.659	127.1	127.4	157.5
2	74.5	2.38	6.50	0.632	127.1	127.3	164.2
3	66.7	2.52	6.77	0.606	127.6	127.1	171.2
4	56.6	2.71	7.37	0.587	127.5	129.4	186.2
5	44.9	3.00	7.95	0.509	128.1	125.3	201.0

TABLE 2a—COMPOSITION OF EXTERNAL SOLUTION (Na) VARYING (Cl) CONSTANT

K_0 (in θ) = 43.3
 K in eqn. (10) = 1.65

Expt. No.	Conc. of gum C	pH of solution in colloid chamber	$[(Na^+)] \times 10^3$	θ	Excess con. $D_w \times 10^3$	Osmotic pressure in cm. H_2O		
						Observed	Calculated from	
							Author's eqn. (10)	Briggs eqn. (5b)
6	38.1	3.39	6.46	0.468	9.90	128.8	126.1	250.0
7	31.7	4.03	7.21	0.423	15.37	129.5	129.3	388.3
8	28.2	5.79	7.82	0.395	18.68	129.0	129.3	472.0

TABLE 3—COMPOSITION OF EXTERNAL SOLUTION (CL) VARYING (NA) VARYING

K_0 (in θ) = 43.3

K in eqn. (11) = 6.57

Expt. No.	Conc. of gum C	pH of solution in colloid chamber	θ	Excess con. $D_w \times 10^3$	[(Na) - (Cl)] $\times 10^3$	Osmotic pressure in cm. H ₂ O		
						Observed	Calculated from	
							Authors' eqn. (11)	Briggs eqn. (5b)
1	18.6	5.31	0.300	12.69	2.656	131.5	132.3	320.5
2	18.8	5.21	0.303	13.62	2.601	130.8	131.0	344.1
3	20.0	5.13	0.316	13.91	2.490	131.5	130.7	351.5
4	22.3	4.77	0.340	15.20	2.321	131.2	131.2	381.9
5	23.8	4.63	0.355	15.77	2.240	131.0	132.0	398.5

TABLE 3A—COMPOSITION OF EXTERNAL SOLUTION (CL) VARYING, (NA) VARYING

K_0 (in θ) = 43.3

K in eqn. (6) = 1.04

Expt. No.	Con. of gum C	pH of solution in colloid chamber	θ	Excess con. $D_w \times 10^3$	Osmotic pressure in con. H ₂ O		
					Observed	Calculated from	
						Authors' eqn. (6)	Briggs eqn. (5b)
6	36	3.72	0.454	11.02	130.4	131.5	278.4
7	59	3.12	0.577	8.58	130.4	130.2	217.0
8	75	2.92	0.634	7.72	130.1	128.6	195.2

Discussion

An examination of the tables shows that the observed values of osmotic pressure are always much smaller than those calculated by Briggs using equation (5b). It, however, appears from the data in the tables 1, 2 and 3a that the agreement between the observed values of osmotic pressure and those calculated from equation (6), deduced by the author, is quite satisfactory. It, therefore, follows that it is not D_w but θKD_w which is equal to D of equation (2c) or (5).

The data recorded in table 2a have been obtained by Briggs under conditions in which the concentration of HCl and the applied external pressure have been kept constant, but the concentration of NaOH has been varied. It will be noticed that the agreement between the observed and the calculated values of osmotic pressure using equation (10) is fairly satisfactory. In equation (10) $i(\text{Na}^+)$ may be taken as proportional to the expression within the square bracket in equation (8).

The data recorded in table 3 have been obtained under conditions in which the applied external pressure only has been kept constant, while the concentrations of HCl, NaOH and that of the gum

have been varied. The equation (11) includes terms representing each of these variables. $[(\text{Na}^+) - (\text{Cl}^-)]$ in equation (11) has been taken as proportional to the expression within the square bracket in equation (8). It will be noted that the agreement between the observed values of osmotic pressure and those calculated from equation (11) is quite satisfactory.

It may be pointed out that in table 2 expt. no. 8 of Briggs paper there is a printing error, NaOH used should be 1.002×10^{-3} equiv. instead of 0.1002×10^{-3} equiv.

References

1. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 367.
2. O. STERN, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1924, **30**, 50.
3. J. N. MUKHERJEE, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1920-21, **16**, 103.
4. M. G. GOUY, *J. Physique*, 1910, **9**, 457.
5. D. L. CHAPMAN, *Phil. Mag.*, 1913, **25**, 475.
6. F. G. DONNAN, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1911, **17**, 572.
7. F. W. KLAARENBECK, *Colloid Science*, Elsevier Publishing Company Inc., 1963, Edition, Vol. 1, p. 191.
8. J. TH. G. OVERBECK, *Progress in Biophysics and Biophysical Chemistry*, Pergamon Press, London, 1956, vol. 6, p. 72.
9. D. R. BRIGGS, *J. Phys. Chem.* 1934, **38**, 1145.